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STURM-Flood: a curated dataset for deep learning-based flood extent mapping leveraging Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery

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ABSTRACT

Flooding is a major global natural disaster exacerbated by climate change and urbanization. Timely assessment and mapping of inundations are crucial for preventive and emergency measures, driving the demand for curated global geospatial data to implement novel algorithms. This study introduces the STURM-Flood dataset, a high-quality, open-access, and DL-ready resource for flood extent mapping using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, combined with ground-truth data from the Copernicus Emergency Management Service. The dataset encompasses 21,602 Sentinel-1 tiles and 2,675 Sentinel-2 tiles, each measuring 128×128 pixels at 10 m resolution, alongside corresponding water masks covering 60 flood events globally. Two U-Net models evaluated the dataset: Sentinel-1 achieved 83.61% test accuracy and 0.8327 weighted F1-score, while Sentinel-2 yielded 92.75% test accuracy and 0.9243 weighted F1-score. These results underscore the dataset's potential in developing robust models for water extent mapping. STURM-Flood dataset aims to provide a valuable resource for research and development in flood mapping and disaster management. Future research could focus on expanding and refining different approaches and data sources for broader applications. The reference data and code are openly available in the Zenodo repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12748983> and GitHub repository <https://github.com/STURM-WEO/STURM-Flood>.

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1. Introduction

In the last decades, flooding has figured as the most frequent and widespread natural disaster on a global scale (Pesaresi et al., 2017), constituting an average of 38% of all recorded emergency events between 1990 and 2024 (CRED-IRSS-UCLouvain, 2023). Furthermore, climate change may increase frequency and intensity of floods (IPCC, 2012): extreme weather events have been ranked in The Global Risks Report 2022 by

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the World Economic Forum (2022) as the most critical threat to the world in short term (0–2 years) and one of the top three in both medium (2–5 years) and long term (5–10 years) by severity of impacts on societies, economies, and the planet. Together with worsening climate change trends, increasingly high density of population and infrastructure in urban areas worldwide (Competence Centre on Foresight, 2020) exacerbates vulnerability and exposure (Ceola et al., 2014). Artificial impervious and near impervious surfaces alter the hydrological cycle with increased peak flows, variable surface run-off volumes and flow, decreased infiltration and shorter lag times (Fletcher et al., 2013). The dramatic events that occurred in Europe and China during the summer of 2021 (FloodList, 2021; United Nations, 2021) vividly highlight the profound impacts of floods, including loss of life, socio-economic disruptions, and environmental damage, especially in urbanized areas.

Addressing these challenges demands timely assessment and mapping of different types of floods, especially in urban and anthropized areas. Maps of the observed inundation extent during or after an event, along with susceptibility and hazard maps, are crucial for both preventive and emergency measures (Bentivoglio et al., 2022). There is an exigent demand for cost-effective techniques to fill data and knowledge gaps at the urban scale to protect the most vulnerable territories (Wilby, 2019). The European Directive on the assessment and management of flood risks promotes improved mapping along with the rights of public access to information and participation (EUR-Lex-Document 32017D0863-EN, 2017; European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2003).

In this context, Remote Sensing (RS) represents a not fully exploited potential for mapping and monitoring (Domeneghetti et al., 2019): free optical and SAR imagery can provide flood-related information both during and after a disaster. Moreover, novel computational techniques based on AI such as ML and DL can yield valuable information in the field of RS (European Commission Joint Research Centre., 2021; Yuan et al., 2021) and in particular flood extent or inundation mapping (Bentivoglio et al., 2022). (All abbreviations are listed at the end of the full text.)

1.1. Flood extent mapping from satellite imagery

The progress in satellite RS provides an increasing number of resources at the global scale (Yimer et al., 2023), supplying timely and reliable maps of flood extent (Domeneghetti et al., 2019), but data can be expensive and difficult to acquire due to their observation frequency and weather conditions (Bentivoglio et al., 2022). EO-based mapping of hydrological response and resulting flood in urban and suburban areas (Muszynski et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2019; Wirion et al., 2017) is difficult due to morphological complexity, thus prior work in this field is limited.

The European Copernicus Programme offers complete, free, and open access to satellite EO data. Managed by the European Commission in partnership with the ESA and other organizations, the Copernicus EO component relies on the dedicated Sentinel satellites and contributing missions, fostering many applications. Sentinel data, specifically Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, have proven their usefulness for flood mapping (Tarpanelli et al., 2022) due to their spatial resolution up to 10 m, short revisit time, and rapid product delivery (European Space Agency, 2024a). Applications for estimating the extent of the flooded areas use imagery from Sentinel-1 (Chini et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2021; Lin et al.,

2019; Mason et al., 2021; Saleh et al., 2020; Vanama et al., 2020), Sentinel-2 (Portalés-Julìà et al., 2023; Yokoya et al., 2020) or both (Bai et al., 2021; Rudner et al., 2019) to overcome the limitation of optical imagery, such as cloud cover, and SAR imagery, such as non-linearities in signal reflectance (Konapala et al., 2021), particularly in anthropized and urban scenarios characterized by mixed land-use and dense infrastructure (Muszynski et al., 2022). The variety of recent literature indicate a lively emerging research area where there is much potential to improve urban flood mapping with newly available data and computation techniques.

1.2. Available datasets

The task of identifying and delineating the extent of flooded areas within satellite or aerial imagery can be achieved through the analysis of the perceptual aspects that determine whether a portion of a raster image belongs to a condition of “presence of flood” or “absence of flood”. Thus, in terms of CV, the scenario of interest is a case of semantic segmentation, where each pixel in the given raster image is classified into a distinct semantic class, typically using ML or DL algorithms (Yu et al., 2018). Such models are increasingly employed due to their effectiveness in capturing the spatial characteristics of floods (Bentivoglio et al., 2022) but usually require large amounts of high-quality labeled data to achieve good performances.

Despite the advancements in RS-based method over the past years, observed data remain often limited and specific to particular study areas, compared to hydrological-hydraulic models and simulations. The lack of a unified framework to compare different approaches could be addressed by creating benchmark datasets tailored to specific mapping applications (Bentivoglio et al., 2022). Open, up-to-date datasets and shared, reliable tools are critical to face the global hydrological challenges of the 2030s and beyond (Wilby, 2019).

The growing body of literature on hydrological extremes from a global perspective reflects the expanding number of applications enabled by novel processing capabilities and advancements in open-access satellite and geospatial data (Lindersson et al., 2020).

As we consider flood extent mapping a semantic segmentation task, we excluded the studies using datasets with boolean labelling (i.e. flood/no flood) for entire tiles rather than pixel-level labelling, e.g. Sen12-Flood (Rambour et al., 2020), commercial or not-georeferenced, e.g. Floodnet (Rahnemoonfar et al., 2020).

To identify the datasets currently publicly available for flood extent mapping from RS, the following parameters were used: adherence to the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), global or near-global geographic coverage, quality.

Table 1 provides a summary of the existing resources, highlighting their primary features, including data source, type, size, spatial resolution, and number of observed events.

Existing datasets have proven valuable in various studies, as demonstrated by the extensive reuse of Sen1Flod11 (Bonafilia et al., 2020). Despite their usefulness, their immediate applicability in operational settings is constrained by limitations in data size, consistency, and DL-readiness. For instance, no-data regions, such as areas obscured by clouds or noise, reduce the usable dataset and necessitate additional preprocessing. The availability of multiple, comparable datasets enhances research outcomes, as demonstrated by Portalés-Julìà et al. (2024), by mitigating biases in individual datasets, improving accessibility and reusability for the global research community.

Table 1. Overview of available datasets and their main characteristics.

Dataset	Data Source	Format	Size - Res.	Number of events	Reference
Kuro Siwo	Sentinel-1, SRTM DEM, manual annotation	GeoTIFF	67490 timeseries 224×224 10m res.	53	Bountos et al. (2024)
UrbanSAR Floods	Sentinel-1, Semi-automatic annotation	GeoTIFF	8879 tiles 512×512 10m res.	18	Zhao et al. (2024)
WorldFloods	Sentinel-2, CopernicusEMS, UNOSAT, GLOFMIR	GeoJSON, GeoTIFF	509 pairs 10m res.	144	Portalés-Julà et al. (2023)
MMFlood	Sentinel-1, MapZen DEM, CopernicusEMS, OpenStreetMap Hydrography ^a	GeoTIFF	1748 pairs max. 2000×2000 20m res.	95	Montello et al. (2022)
Sen1Flood11	Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, manual annotation	GeoTIFF	446 ^b tiles 512×512 10m res.	11	Bonafilia et al. (2020)
UNOSAT Flood	Sentinel-1, UNOSAT	GeoTIFF	58128 tiles 256×256 10m res.	15	Nemni et al. (2020)

^aIf present. ^b4381 including weakly-labeled data.

We developed STURM-Flood dataset with these factors in mind to provide an additional resource for flood mapping research that can be used as is or in combination with the existing materials. This work aims to provide an open, accessible, global, fine-grained, DL-ready dataset for deploying broadly applicable models that can be particularly beneficial for vulnerable and data-scarce areas.

2. Material and methods

The core steps included data retrieval and preparation, models implementation and training, and test performance evaluation. The workflow was implemented using free and open source tools, namely Python (Van Rossum & Drake, 1995), GDAL geospatial library, Tensorflow (TensorFlow Developers, 2024), and Keras (Chollet, 2015). The models were trained and optimized in the Amazon Web Services (AWS Documentation, 2024) cloud infrastructure.

The following subsections describe each step employed in curating the dataset and training the U-Net baseline models for semantic segmentation.

2.1. Data acquisition and preprocessing

2.1.1. Flood events data

The data relative to the hydrography and flooded areas were sourced from the Copernicus EMS mapping services (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2020). The Copernicus EMS leverages satellite imagery and other geospatial data to provide free mapping services for natural and anthropogenic disasters, covering all phases of the emergency management cycle by Rapid Mapping and Risk and Recovery Mapping temporal modes. The service is activated only upon request from authorized users, e.g. civil protection agencies, focusing on areas where the impact on human populations, infrastructure, and assets is substantial. Consequently, EMS maps are frequently activated in response to disasters in highly anthropized areas, as these regions tend to have greater exposure to risk. While the quality of EMS maps has been questioned in some studies due to the rapid timeframes required for flood response (Bountos et al., 2024), particularly in

earlier activations when automatic models were less refined, EMS data remains a valuable source. It provides standardized and timely geospatial data that undergoes rigorous validation processes (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2020) and extensive coverage. Its proven effectiveness in mapping flood extents makes it a suitable choice for ground truthing (Montello et al., 2022; Portalés-Julià et al., 2023).

The EMS flood activation records were filtered starting from January 1, 2016 to ensure Sentinel coverage, and excluding open EMS activations to ensure only events with production finished and quality approved were processed. The resulting list of EMSR codes representing different flood events was further refined based on the availability of the standardized spatial datasets delivered by the Rapid Mapping service. This process identified 131 EMSR codes, each containing multiple downloadable vector packages. For each EMSR code and AOI, floodmaps and related metadata were automatically processed starting from the layers included in the vector packages of delineation and monitoring (European Commission Joint Research Centre., 2020): activation and imagery metadata containing information about sources and AOI, crisis information layers containing information about the observed event, and ancillary base layers containing information about hydrography. The floodmaps were reprojected to the appropriate UTM zone and associated with Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 products within a defined time window (72 hours from Sentinel-2 and 48 hours for Sentinel-1, to reflect their different revisit time) and 70% cloud coverage threshold for Sentinel 2. Within each group of floodmaps referring to the same EMSR code and AOI, we selected the flood map with the shortest time difference to mitigate potential misalignments between the observable flood extent and the reference data. The selected floodmaps were rasterized with a pixel size of 10 m, to match the resolution of Sentinel data. The water-related features were automatically categorized using predefined dictionaries mapping vector attributes, i.e. element type (European Commission Joint Research Centre., 2020), to the following classes:

- Class 0: Coastline and area of interest.
- Class 1: Flooded areas.
- Class 2: River-related features such as rivers, river banks, and streams.
- Class 3: Open water.
- Class 4: Reservoirs.
- Class 5: Lakes.
- Class 99: No data.

The raster floodmaps were clipped to the original AOI polygon included in the EMS vector package to ensure that only relevant areas were included.

A comprehensive validation process was implemented to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the processed data, including checks for georeferencing, attribute correctness, and temporal alignment.

Figure 1 shows the geographic distribution by country of the flood events represented by the 60 EMSR codes selected for generating the dataset.

Table 2 summarizes the classification of flood events using to the Degree of Urbanisation, which combines criteria for land cover, population density, and spatial contiguity (European Commission & Eurostat, 2021). Each flood event was mapped to GHS Settlement Model epoch: 2020 (European Commission & Joint Research Centre, 2023) and classified as urban if it intersected Urban Centre, Dense Urban Cluster, or Semi-Dense Urban Cluster cells; suburban if it intersected Suburban Grid Cell; and rural if they

Figure 1. Countries affected by the EMSR flood events used for the dataset generation.

Table 2. Flood events by degree of urbanization.

	Number of events	
	Sentinel-1-EMS pairs	Sentinel-2-EMS pairs
Urban	39	17
Suburban	2	4
Rural	6	8
Total	47	29

Table 3. Overview of the STURM-Flood datasets and its main characteristics.

Dataset	Data Source	Format	Size – Res.	Bands	Events
STURM-Flood	Sentinel-1, CopernicusEMS	GeoTIFF	21,602 tiles 128 × 128 10 m res	VV, VH	49
	Sentinel-2, CopernicusEMS	GeoTIFF	2,675 tiles 128 × 128 10 m res	B2, B3, B4, B5, B6, B7, B8, B11, B12	29

intersected only Rural Cluster, Low Density Rural Grid Cell, or Very Low Density Grid Cell cells. The classification shows that the majority of the dataset's flood events involve urban areas (83% for Sentinel-1, 59% for Sentinel-2), with the remaining events distributed across rural (13% Sentinel-1, 28% Sentinel-2) and suburban areas (1% Sentinel-1, 8% Sentinel-2).

2.1.2. Sentinel-1 data

The preprocessing of Sentinel-1 imagery is a crucial step to produce high-quality, reliable imagery suitable for flood extent mapping. This process involves corrections and adjustments to address geometric and radiometric distortions, reduce noise, and enhance image quality.

The preprocessing steps were implemented using the SNAP Sentinel-1 toolbox (European Space Agency, 2024b).

The workflow included: *Thermal Noise Removal* to ensure variations are due to surface features rather than noise artefacts; *Apply Orbit File* to improve geolocation accuracy; *Border Noise Removal* to discard low-intensity noise and invalid data at the edges of the scene; *Calibration* radiometric correction to ensure accurate radar backscatter representation; *Range Doppler Terrain Correction* to compensate for geometric distortions from topographical variations and satellite tilt; *Refined Lee Speckle Filtering* to reduce the granular noise that inherently affects SAR imagery. Additionally, the data was converted from a linear scale to decibels (dB) to manage the high dynamic range typically present in SAR data, improving the visual quality and thus the accuracy of subsequent analyses.

The output of this phase is a set of 2-band composite rasters with a spatial resolution of 10 m, where the VV polarization captures surface roughness characteristics, and the VH polarization provides additional structural details for enhanced scene interpretation. The rasters were clipped according to the floodmaps obtained for each EMS code and AOI where Sentinel-1 data were available.

2.1.3. Sentinel-2 data

The preprocessing of Sentinel-2 imagery is paramount for data quality and reliability in DL applications, mainly due to potential cloud coverage obscuring substantial portions of the images, especially during adverse weather related events such as floods, and the varying spatial resolutions of its 13 spectral bands.

The bands chosen for the analysis encompass the visible and near-infrared bands (B2, B3, B4, B8) with spatial resolutions of 10 m, the red edge and shortwave infrared bands (B5, B6, B7, B11, B12) with spatial resolutions of 20 m. The remaining bands were excluded as they contain information primarily relevant for atmospheric studies (B1, B9, B10 with lower spatial resolution of 60 m) or vegetation analysis (B8a with spatial resolutions of 20 m).

The preprocessing workflow begins with the creation of a cloud-shadow mask using open source tools developed by KappaZeta Ltd (2023) (Domnich et al., 2021) to identify and remove areas covered by clouds.

Following cloud masking, all Sentinel-2 bands were aligned to a uniform spatial resolution of 10 m to ensure the creation of consistent multi-band images. The band sharpening process was performed on 256×256 pixel tiles to manage computational resources efficiently and ensure the precision of the sharpening algorithm. The band sharpening was performed using the *pyDMS: a Python Data Mining Sharpener implementation* repository (Guzinski, 2024), a tool implementing a decision tree based algorithm based on the methodology by Gao et al. (2012). Thus, high-resolution Sentinel-2 bands served as the reference data for the Data Mining Sharpener algorithm to sharpen the lower-resolution bands.

The outputs of the preprocessing workflow are 256×256 9-bands composite tiles with a spatial resolution of 10 m, clipped according to the floodmaps.

2.2. Dataset preparation for ML and DL applications

The preparation workflow for both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 based datasets follows a structured approach to ensure high-quality, consistent, and reliable data for analysis.

To enable systematic handling and processing of tile pairs throughout the study, the correspondence between the Sentinel composites and their respective raster floodmaps, to be used as segmentation masks, was verified systematically.

The dataset preparation key steps, involved tile creation, normalization, mask remapping, validation and sanity checks as follows:

(1) Tiles were created from the original Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 datasets and their corresponding masks derived from Copernicus EMS at a size of 128×128 pixels and 10 m resolution to facilitate the subsequent steps for the segmentation task. The smaller tile size allows tiles with no-data pixels or without water pixels to be accurately identified and discarded without dramatic data loss. Additionally, this tile size preserves feature complexity while reducing computational load on processors and memory, enabling faster and more efficient processing steps. This approach remains robust to data sparsity and computational complexity, even in large-scale geospatial studies.

(2) Normalization of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 images involved linearly rescaling pixel values to a consistent range while preserving their original relationships. The min-max normalization ranges, applied across all image channels, were empirically determined based on observed data values: -30 to 10 for Sentinel-1 and 400 to 1600 for Sentinel-2.

(3) To facilitate the creation of our baseline models, we performed binary remapping of the masks for both datasets, aggregating the original classes according to predefined legends. This process simplified the masks into two categories: water (including Flooded Area, River, Open Water, Reservoir, Lake) and non-water pixels. Despite this simplification, we provide the original raster data with values corresponding to the classes mentioned in 2.1.1, allowing users with more sophisticated models to utilize the detailed class information as needed.

(4) Extensive validation steps were implemented throughout the preparation phase to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the processed tiles. This included: tile pair matching (images/masks) by filenames and geo-extents; ensuring dimensional consistency (128×128 pixels), band counts (2 for Sentinel-1, 9 for Sentinel-2), mask class numbers against defined legends; removing tile pairs if any no-data pixels are present in either or both tiles, (e.g. due to cloud removal or missing values); selection of the pairs where the mask had a water coverage above a threshold of 1% to better focus on relevant data and slightly mitigate class imbalance.

After the validation, a small number of instances were discarded due to image dimension incompatibilities, whereas the primary reason for entry exclusion was water percentage below the established threshold of 1%.

Figure 2 illustrates the frequency distribution of water percentage in satellite imagery samples. The vertical dashed line demarcates the 1% threshold. The histogram reveals a skewed distribution, with a predominant peak at the lower end of the water percentage scale. This distribution pattern indicates that the dataset predominantly consists of images with low water coverage, while fully aquatic scenes are relatively rare. The distribution captures diverse scenarios of both permanent hydrography and flood events, though it may require strategies to address potential class imbalance for optimal algorithm performance.

For the dataset employing Sentinel-1 imagery in conjunction with EMS tiles, a total of 56,810 were initially processed, of which 21,602 were deemed valid, while the remaining

(a) Distribution of water pixels % in the pairs of Sentinel-1 images and EMS masks.

(b) Distribution of water pixels % in the pairs of Sentinel-2 images and EMS masks.

Figure 2. Distribution of water percentage in the processed tiles. The dashed line represents the 1% threshold used for filtering.

35,208 entries were discarded predominantly due to water percentage thresholds. The water pixel percentage in the valid tile masks ranges from the minimum threshold 1% to a maximum of 100.00%, with an average of 29.28% and a standard deviation of 34.32%.

For the dataset based on Sentinel-2 imagery combined with EMS tiles, out of 4213 processed entries, 2675 were deemed valid, while 1538 were excluded. The water percentage distribution ranges from 1% to 100.00%, with a mean of 27.58% and a standard deviation of 29.20%.

The dataset size difference between Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 arises from the different revisit times and the nature of SAR and optical data acquisition (Table 3). Sentinel-1's shorter revisit time and SAR imaging allow it to capture data regardless of weather, resulting in more available images. In contrast, Sentinel-2's has a longer revisit time and optical data is often impacted by cloud cover, and many activations had to be excluded due to timing mismatches with flood events and weather obstructions, leading to fewer usable tiles.

Figure 3 shows the average percentages for each land cover class by event across the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 datasets, derived from ESA's WorldCover 2021 data (Zanaga et al., 2022). The built-up land cover percentage within individual tiles varied significantly, ranging from 0.0% to 94.2% in Sentinel-1 tiles and from 0.0% to 90.5% in Sentinel-2 tiles, reflecting the diversity of urban, suburban, and non-urban areas captured within the datasets.

(a) Average % for each land cover class by event in the pairs of Sentinel-1 images and EMS masks.

(b) Average % for each land cover class by event in the pairs of Sentinel-2 images and EMS masks.

Figure 3. Average percentage for each land cover class by event.

3. Results

3.1. Structure of the final dataset

To maintain a systematic and easily interpretable file structure, each image and mask GeoTIFF tile adhere to the file naming scheme *EMSRCODE_AOICODE_XXX.tif* (e.g. *EMSR416_AOI02_09_05_2_1.tif*), as follows:

- *EMSRCODE* represents the event ID according to the Copernicus EMS naming convention. It helps identify the specific flood event.
- *AOICODE* represents the AOI ID, again following the Copernicus naming convention. It indicates the specific geographic area affected by the event.
- *[0-9_]* include numbers and underscores to ensure that each file is uniquely identifiable if related to the same event and area.

The folder structure can be schematized as follows:

```

STURM-Flood/
├── Dataset/
│   ├── Sentinel11/
│   │   ├── S1/
│   │   │   └── floodmaps/
│   │   └── Sentinel12/
│   │       ├── S2/
│   │       │   └── floodmaps/
│   └── Sentinel11_metadata.csv
│   └── Sentinel12_metadata.csv

```

Figure 4 shows a Sentinel-1 sample tile, with the SAR image, water mask, and their overlay.

Similarly, Figure 5 provides a Sentinel-2 sample tile, showing the RGB composite, water mask, and their overlay.

To feed the networks for the baseline models, the final set of instances was divided into non-overlapping subsets with an 80:10:10 ratio for training, validation, and testing, as shown in Table 4, providing a balanced trade-off between effective learning and overfitting prevention. This split was applied randomly across all

Figure 4. Sample tile from the STURM-Dataset: Sentinel-1 VV polarization (left), water mask (centre), and an overlay of both (right).

Figure 5. Sample tile from the STURM-Dataset: Sentinel-2 RGB composite (left), water mask (centre), and an overlay of both (right).

Table 4. Data split ratios for training, validation, and test subset.

Subset	Percentage	Number of Instances	
		Sentinel-1-EMS pairs	Sentinel-2- EMS pairs
Training	80%	17,282	2,141
Validation	10%	2,160	267
Test	10%	2,160	267
Total		21,602	2,675

events to expose the model to diverse flood scenarios and ensure varied representation within each subset. This approach was chosen for its simplicity and ability to provide a generalized assessment of model performances, while leaving alternative strategies like regional or event-based holdouts as a potential avenue for future studies focused on model-specific evaluation.

3.2. Dataset evaluation on baseline models

To determine whether the dataset provides sufficient and relevant information for reliable mapping outcomes, we implemented and evaluated two U-Net models, each trained on data from the two different Sentinel satellites.

U-Net was chosen because it is a well-established DL architecture for semantic segmentation tasks (Ronneberger et al., 2015) and several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of U-Net and its variants for RS image segmentation (Li et al., 2024), particularly for flood extent mapping using remote sensing data (Konapala et al., 2021; Mateo-Garcia et al., 2021; Muszynski et al., 2022; Tavus et al., 2022; Wieland & Martinis, 2019; Zhao et al., 2022).

The U-Net architecture (Figure 6) consists of the following key components:

- Convolutional Downsampling Blocks (Encoder): Each block contains two convolutional layers with ReLU activation, optional batch normalization, and dropout, followed by max pooling to reduce spatial dimensions.
- Convolutional Upsampling Blocks (Decoder): Each block uses transposed convolutions for upsampling, concatenates with the corresponding encoder block output (skip connection), and passes through two convolutional layers with ReLU activation.

Figure 6. Overview of U-Net architecture.

- **Final Convolutional Layer:** Produces the output segmentation map with a softmax activation function to generate pixel-wise class probabilities.

The semantic segmentation of water and non-water pixels was treated as a specific multi-class problem with two distinct classes. This means that the models are trained to classify each pixel into one of the two classes, and in terms of implementation, the models utilize a softmax activation function to convert the raw scores into probabilities and categorical loss functions.

The loss functions employed for hyperparameter optimization were Categorical Cross-Entropy, Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy (1) to addresses class imbalance by focusing more on hard-to-classify examples (Lin et al., 2018), and Weighted Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy, each adapted for the two-class problem of water and non-water pixels and implemented as follows:

$$\text{loss} = - \sum_{i=1}^C \alpha_i (1 - p_i)^\gamma t_i \log(p_i + \varepsilon) \quad (1)$$

where

- t_i and p_i are, respectively, the ground-truth and the predicted probability for each class i in $C = 2$;
- $(1 - p_t)^\gamma$ is the modulating factor;
- α_i : $\alpha = 0.25$ is the weight assigned to class i to prevent the loss function from being dominated by the prevalent classes in the dataset for the Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy (Lin et al., 2018) or α_i class-specific weights computed inversely proportional to the frequency of each pixel class for the Weighted Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy;
- $\gamma = 2.0$ is the focusing parameter, chosen based on Lin et al. (2018), to effectively balance the focus on hard-to-classify examples;
- $\varepsilon = 1 \times 10^{-7}$ is a small constant added to ensure numerical stability.

These pixel-level loss functions (Azad et al., 2023) are particularly effective in addressing class imbalance and improving model semantic segmentation performance.

The benefit of this approach is that it provides greater flexibility for future expansions, allowing for a smoother transition to multi-class classification should the problem domain broaden (e.g. considering flooded area and hydrography separately or integrate land cover classes).

3.2.1. U-Net trained on Sentinel-1

The training set (Table 4) consisted of ordered pairs of 128×128 pixel normalized input tiles derived from Sentinel-1 imagery and corresponding binary masks, where class 0 represented *non-water* and class 1 represented *water* pixels. A separate validation set (Table 4) was used to provide an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance during both training and Bayesian hyperparameter optimization, thereby preserving its generalization ability.

The configurations for initial training, hyperparameter tuning, and the best model obtained are summarized in Table 5.

Figure 7 illustrates the training results, where the x-axis represents the number of epochs, and the y-axes indicate the accuracy and loss values for the training set (teal line) and the validation set (maroon line). Initially, the training accuracy increases rapidly, stabilizing at approximately 81.5% after around 10 epochs, indicating effective learning from the training data. The validation accuracy, although fluctuating, eventually stabilizes at a slightly lower value of around 81.3%. The best trained model reached a final accuracy of 81.55% on the training set and 82.27% on the validation set and a loss of 0.031 and

Table 5. Summary of initial training configuration and hyperparameter tuning results.

Configuration			
Input Data Categories	128 × 128 pixel tiles, 10 m resolution, 2 bands (VV and VH) 2 (Water, Non-Water)		
	Initial Training	Hyperparameter Tuning	Best Model
Batch Size	32	16, 32, 64	64
Dropout Rate	0.2	0.1 to 0.7 (continuous)	0.6885339274193293
Weight Decay	0.05	0.05 to 0.2 (continuous)	0.07490734006875711
Epochs	20	60 to 90	70
Loss Functiona	CCE	CCE, CFCE, Weighted CFCE	CFCE
Optimizer	adam		
Learning Rate	0.001		
Number of Blocks	5	4, 5, 6	6
Objective		Maximize validation accuracy	
Trainable parameters			34,516,866

^aCategorical Cross-Entropy (CCE), Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy (CFCE).

(a) Training and validation accuracy.

(b) Training and validation loss.

Figure 7. Training and validation of the U-Net model for flood mapping using Sentinel-1 imagery over 70 epochs. The maroon lines represent the training values, while the teal lines represent the validation values.

0.030, respectively. The patterns in the validation accuracy and loss, despite some initial variability, suggests that the model generalizes reasonably well but could benefit from additional regularization techniques to improve stability.

To obtain an unbiased estimate of the quality of the segmentation predictions on new pictures, the trained model was applied to an independent test dataset, each pixel was assigned to the class with the highest probability. A pixel-wise confusion matrix (Table 6) was constructed over the entire test set opposing the pixels in a predicted class (model response) against the pixels in an actual class.

The accuracy of the model on the test set is 83.61%. To measure the inference capabilities, several metrics are calculated, as reported in Table 7. These results are consistent with the training and validation phase.

Figure 8 displays a sample of inference from the Sentinel-1 test set, showing the SAR image, the binary water mask, and a contingency map (right) obtained from a pixel-to-pixel comparison between the inference and the ground truth. The TP – correctly identified water pixels – are shown in blue, the FP – pixels incorrectly identified as water – are shown in red, and the FN – missed water pixels – are shown in yellow.

Table 6. Pixel-wise confusion matrix for the test set.

Predicted	Actual	
	Non-Water	Water
Non-Water	22 823 797	2 269 604
Water	3 514 866	6 682 869

Table 7. Pixel-wise evaluation metrics for the test set.

Metric		Non-Water	Water	Macro avg	Weighted avg
Precision ^a	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$	86.66%	74.65%	78.24%	83.18%
Recall ^a	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$	90.96%	65.53%	80.65%	83.61%
F1-Score	$F_1 = \frac{2 \times \text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$	0.8875	0.6979	0.7927	0.8327

^aTrue Positive (TP); False Positive (FP); True Negative (TN); False Negative (FN).

Figure 8. Sample from the test dataset: Sentinel-1 VV polarization (left), binary water mask (center), and contingency map (right). True positives (TP) are shown in blue, false positives (FP) in red, and false negatives (FN) in yellow.

3.2.2. U-Net trained on Sentinel-2

The dataset and U-Net models used for mapping flood extent from Sentinel-2 imagery share key characteristics with those used for Sentinel-1 imagery, inherent to the segmentation task in RS data. Analogously, the instance inputs consisted of ordered pairs of normalized 128×128 pixel input tiles derived from Sentinel-2 data and their corresponding binary masks, where class 0 represented *non-water* and class 1 represented *water* pixels.

The training, validation, and test strategies were analogous for both models, ensuring a consistent approach in the evaluation. However, due to differences in the size of available data, the initial training model was trained with slightly different parameters, i.e. smaller batch size and increased number of epochs. In each case, a separate validation set was employed to improve generalization during both training and Bayesian hyperparameter optimization.

The configurations for initial training, hyperparameter tuning, and the best models obtained are summarized in the [Table 8](#).

[Figure 9](#) shows training and validation loss of the best model over 83 epochs. In the first couple of epochs, both training and validation accuracies were observed to be around 83–84%, likely due to class imbalance and the random prediction of the majority class (non-water). As training progressed, a notable improvement in both training and validation accuracy was observed, reaching above 90% within a few epochs. The steady increase in accuracies and the rapid decrease in losses suggest that the model is learning effectively and generalizing well without severe overfitting.

The final metrics of the model are as follows: the training accuracy was 93.22%, while the validation accuracy was 92.28%; the training loss was 0.0149, and the validation loss was 0.0157. Further detailed exploration of hyperparameter tuning could potentially enhance these results.

The confusion matrix presented in [Table 9](#) provides an overview of the performance of the model on the test hold-out set.

Table 8. Summary of initial training configuration and hyperparameter tuning results.

Configuration			
Input Data	128 × 128 pixel tiles, 10 m resolution,		
Categories	9 bandsharpened bands (B02, B03, B04, B08, B05, B06, B07, B11, B12)		
	2 (Water, Non-Water)		
	Initial Training	Hyperparameter Tuning	Best Model
Batch Size	4	16, 32, 64	64
Dropout Rate	0.2	0.1 to 0.7 (continuous)	0.6885339274193293
Weight Decay	0.05	0.05 to 0.2 (continuous)	0.07490734006875711
Epochs	30	40 to 90	83
Loss Function ^a	CCE	CCE, CFCE, Weighted CFCE	CFCE
Optimizer	adam		
Learning Rate	0.001	1×10^{-5} to 5×10^{-5} (continuous)	1.9142×10^{-5}
Number of Blocks	5	4, 5, 6	6
Objective		Maximize validation accuracy	
Trainable parameters			34,516,866

^aCategorical Cross-Entropy (CCE), Categorical Focal Cross-Entropy (CFCE).

Figure 9. Training and validation of the U-Net model for flood mapping using Sentinel-2 imagery over 83 epochs. The maroon lines represent the training values, while the teal lines represent the validation values.

Table 9. Pixel-wise confusion matrix for the test set.

Predicted	Actual	
	Non-Water	Water
Non-Water	5 334 757	310 791
Water	219 096	1 000 252

Table 10. Pixel-wise evaluation metrics for the test set.

Metric		Non-Water	Water	Macro avg	Weighted avg
Precision ^a	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$	96.58%	72.59%	84.59%	92.75%
Recall ^a	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$	94.08%	82.49%	88.29%	92.23%
F1-Score	$F_1 = \frac{2 \times \text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$	0.9532	0.7722	0.8627	0.9243

^aTrue Positive (TP); False Positive (FP); True Negative (TN); False Negative (FN).

Table 10 provides a more comprehensive evaluation of the pixel-wise classification performance metrics for the test set.

Figure 10 displays a sample of inference from the Sentinel-2 test set, showing the visible spectrum composite, the binary water mask, and the pixel-wise contingency map.

Both models, despite differences in the size of available data and slight variations in training parameters, achieved high accuracy and demonstrated generalization capabilities. Taken together, the results underscore the effectiveness of the STURM-Flood dataset in training DL models for precise flood extent mapping.

3.2.3. Threshold-based water segmentation

To establish baseline performance for water segmentation, traditional threshold-based methods were applied to the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 test sets. For Sentinel-1, Otsu thresholding (Lee et al., 1990; Otsu, 1979) was used, which automatically determines an optimal threshold to distinguish water from non-water pixels by maximizing inter-class variance. For Sentinel-2, the MNDWI was employed with a literature-based threshold of

Figure 10. Sample from the test dataset: Sentinel-2 RGB composite (left), binary water mask (center), and contingency map (right). True positives (TP) are shown in blue, false positives (FP) in red, and false negatives (FN) in yellow.

0.3 (Du et al., 2016) and a second less conservative threshold of 0.1, utilizing B3 and B11 bands for spectral separation of water bodies from land features.

As shown in Table 11, the threshold baseline methods display notable limitations. Otsu thresholding achieved a precision of 25.22%, a recall of 77.76%, and an F1-score of 0.3808 for the water class. MNDWI performance varied with the threshold. At a 0.3, MNDWI achieved a precision of 90.55%, but a recall of 21.54%, resulting in an F1-score of 0.3480 for the water class. Lowering the threshold to 0.1 improved recall (57.63%) and F1-score (0.6918), albeit with a slight reduction in precision (86.51%).

While Table 11 provides cumulative metrics, Figure 11 presents the distributions of precision, recall, and F1 scores relative to water class across individual tiles in the test sets.

As shown in Figure 11, U-Net models consistently outperformed threshold-based methods. For Sentinel-1 inputs, the U-Net achieved a high median precision, while Otsu thresholding produced values skewed toward the lower range, resulting in poor F1 scores despite a slightly better median recall. For Sentinel-2 inputs, the U-Net demonstrates stable performance across all metrics, whereas the MNDWI threshold-based method varies notably with the threshold. At the 0.3 threshold, MNDWI achieved inconsistent precision values, with recall tightly clustered near zero, indicating systematic under-detection of water areas. Lowering the threshold to 0.1 shifted the distributions upward, with precision surpassing that of the U-Net; however, recall remained lower. Thus, the U-Net consistently achieved higher and more stable F1 scores, while MNDWI exhibited significant variability and lower median values at both thresholds.

Figures 12 and 13 present visual comparisons of U-Net predictions and threshold-based methods (Otsu for Sentinel-1 and MNDWI for Sentinel-2).

Table 11. Pixel-wise evaluation metrics for thresholding methods on the test sets.

Metric	Sentinel-1 (Otsu)		Sentinel-2 (MNDWI) ^a			
			0.3 threshold		0.1 threshold	
	Non-Water	Water	Non-Water	Water	Non-Water	Water
Precision ^b						
Recall ^b						
F1-Score						

^aModified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI).

^bTrue Positive (TP); False Positive (FP); True Negative (TN); False Negative (FN).

Figure 11. Violin plots comparing the distributions of precision, recall, and F1 scores for the water class across all test samples. Segmentation methods using Sentinel-1 data as input, i.e. U-Net and Otsu, are represented in cyan, while Sentinel-2 methods, i.e. U-Net and MNDWI, are represented in purple. Median values are indicated by red lines.

The U-Nets accurately delineated the spatial extent of large, continuous water bodies with minimal fragmentation. However, the models exhibited limitations in case of narrow water features, such as small rivers and canals, and water edges, as evidenced by occasional under-detection (FN) for the former and bidirectional misclassification (FN/FP) for the latter. In comparison, threshold-based methods performed significantly worse, generating more misclassifications and fragmented predictions, particularly in urban and complex environments where radar backscatter effects in Sentinel-1 and spectral confusion in Sentinel-2 are common.

Overall, U-Net models provided greater consistency and robustness across test tiles. In contrast, threshold-based methods remained sensitive to parameter tuning, exhibited higher variability, and achieved less balanced performance.

4. Discussion and conclusion

This study introduced the STURM-Flood dataset, a comprehensive georeferenced dataset, open and ready for use with DL, for flood detection using Sentinel-1 or Sentinel-2 satellites.

To evaluate the dataset's utility in developing robust water segmentation models, we implemented two U-Net architectures trained independently on each satellite's data. The models were trained separately due to the practical constraint that, in real use-case scenarios, both satellite data might not always be available simultaneously due to different revisit times. Additionally, Sentinel-2 data can be affected by cloud cover, and flood events are often associated with adverse weather conditions, further limiting its availability. However, keeping the models similar allows for potential ensembling in future applications.

In comparison with related literature, the model performance observed in this study is broadly consistent with previous benchmarks (Bonafilia et al., 2020; Muszynski et al., 2022) and, in some respects, exceeds them, suggesting the dataset's effectiveness for training deep learning flood segmentation networks. Specifically, our results demonstrate that the Sentinel-2-based U-Net model achieved marginally higher F1-scores for water segmentation compared to the Sentinel-1-based model, aligning with previous findings (Muszynski et al., 2022;

Figure 12. Sample tiles from test dataset. From left to right: Sentinel-1 VV polarization, binary water mask, contingency map from U-Net predictions, and contingency map from Otsu thresholding. True positives (TP) are shown in blue, false positives (FP) in red, and false negatives (FN) in yellow.

Portalés-Julià et al., 2023). Our best U-Net flood segmenters demonstrated improvement over previous models in water-class prediction. For Sentinel-1 data, our model achieved an F1-score for the water class of approximately 0.70 (Table 7), surpassing the 0.41 F1-score reported by Muszynski et al. (2022) on the Sentinel-1 data from the Sen1Flood11 dataset. The Sentinel-2-based model achieved an even higher F1-score of 0.77 (Table 10), outperforming Muszynski et al. (2022), which reported an F1-score of 0.51 on Sentinel-2 data. Both of our single-source models also outperformed the stacked Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data model by Muszynski et al. (2022), which reached an F1-score of 0.53. The observed gains in performance likely stem from the larger dataset size and the exclusion of invalid data (i.e. cloudy regions and missing data), given the similarity in model architecture and loss functions across studies.

Figure 13. Sample tiles from the test dataset. From left to right: Sentinel-2 RGB composite, contingency map from U-Net predictions, and contingency map from MNDWI thresholding at 0.1. True positives (TP) are shown in blue, false positives (FP) in red, and false negatives (FN) in yellow.

However, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The U-Net architectures employed in this study were relatively simple and improvements in the network design could enhance segmentation accuracy. Additionally, the fixed threshold of 0.5 applied to model output scores for the classification of pixels does not represent an optimized cutoff. Conducting a thorough Receiver Operating Characteristic analysis (Powers, 2020) and identifying thresholds using Youden's index (Youden, 1950) could yield more balanced precision-recall trade-offs and improve metrics. Furthermore, the inherently lower support of the water class in the dataset poses challenges for training segmentation models. Although the dataset was filtered to include tiles with a minimum of 1% water pixels, this threshold could be refined to further mitigate class imbalance.

Notwithstanding these limitations, the consistent performance across Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery reaffirms the dataset's quality, providing a reliable foundation for future research and operational flood mapping.

The insights gained from this study can guide further improvements in model training and data preprocessing techniques, ultimately enhancing the precision and utility of flood extent mapping models. Covering a broad range of geographical regions and flood events, the STURM-Flood dataset offers robust training material that can improve the accuracy and efficiency of flood extent mapping algorithms. Its openness and adherence to FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016) principles promotes further research and collaboration within the scientific community. Researchers worldwide can easily use and build upon this data to develop and refine their models, minimizing the burden of data preparation.

Future work could investigate the potentials in multi-class problem domains, i.e. multi-class semantic segmentation of permanent water and flooded water, as well as ablation studies and systematic analysis of the impacts on the accuracy of each band of the composite rasters. To improve the robustness to settlement heterogeneity, future dataset expansion may also include more flood events, integrating data from additional sensors and/or combination with existing datasets. Algorithm comparisons (Notarangelo, Mazzariello, et al., 2021), transfer learning (Notarangelo, Hirano, et al., 2021) and model ensembling could be used to develop novel methods for classification, pre-processing the inputs, or post-processing the outputs. These efforts aim to create a more comprehensive resource to the challenges of flood detection across diverse environmental and climatic conditions. The continued development and enhancement of such datasets are essential for advancing the field of RS and improving the resilience of communities to flood-related disasters. Thus, studies on combinations of different approaches and data would be worthwhile.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOI	Area Of Interest
CV	Computer Vision
DL	Deep Learning
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EMSR	EMS Rapid mapping
EO	Earth Observations
ESA	European Space Agency
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FP	False Positives
FN	False Negatives
MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
ML	Machine Learning
RS	Remote Sensing
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
TN	True Negatives
TP	True Positives

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12748983>. The reference code for accessing and utilizing the dataset is provided in the GitHub repository <https://github.com/STURM-WEO/STURM-Flood>.

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References

- AWS Documentation. (2024). <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/>
- Azad, R., Heidary, M., Yilmaz, K., Hüttemann, M., Karimijafarbigloo, S., Wu, Y., & Merhof, D. (2023). Loss functions in the era of semantic segmentation: A survey and outlook. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.05391>
- Bai, Y., Wu, W., Yang, Z., Yu, J., Zhao, B., Liu, X., Yang, H., Mas, E., & Koshimura, S. (2021). Enhancement of detecting permanent water and temporary water in flood disasters by fusing Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery using deep learning algorithms: Demonstration of Sen1Floods11 benchmark datasets. *Remote Sensing*, 13(11), 2220. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13112220>
- Bentivoglio, R., Iсуfi, E., Jonkman, S. N., & Taormina, R. (2022). Deep learning methods for flood mapping: A review of existing applications and future research directions. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 26(16), 4345–4378. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-26-4345-2022>
- Bonafilia, D., Tellman, B., Anderson, T., & Issenberg, E. (2020). Sen1Floods11: A georeferenced dataset to train and test deep learning flood algorithms for Sentinel-1. *2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)* (pp. 835–845). IEEE, Seattle, WA, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPRW50498.2020.00113>
- Bountos, N. I., Sdraka, M., Zavras, A., Karasante, I., Karavias, A., Herekakis, T., & Papoutsis, I. (2024). Kuro Siwo: 33 billion m2 under the water. A global multi-temporal satellite dataset for rapid flood mapping. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.12056>
- Ceola, S., Laio, F., & Montanari, A. (2014). Satellite nighttime lights reveal increasing human exposure to floods worldwide. *Geophysical Research Letter*, 41(20), 7184–7190. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014GL061859>
- Chini, M., Pelich, R., Pulvirenti, L., Pierdicca, N., Hostache, R., & Matgen, P. (2019). Sentinel-1 InSAR coherence to detect floodwater in urban areas: Houston and hurricane Harvey as a test case. *Remote Sensing*, 11(2), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11020107>
- Chollet, F. (2015). *Keras*. GitHub. <https://github.com/fchollet/keras>
- Competence Centre on Foresight. (2020). *Developments and forecasts on continuing urbanisation*. <https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/foresight/topic/continuing-urbanisation/developments-and-forecasts-on-continuing-urbanisation>
- Copernicus. (2024). <https://www.copernicus.eu/>
- CREG-IRSS-UC Louvain. (2023). *EM-DAT emergency events database*. <https://www.emdat.be/>
- Developers, TensorFlow. (2024). *Tensorflow*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10798587>
- Domeneghetti, A., Schumann, G. J.-P., & Tarpanelli, A. (2019). Preface: Remote sensing for flood mapping and monitoring of flood dynamics. *Remote Sensing*, 11(8), 943. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11080943>
- Domnich, M., Sünter, I., Trofimov, H., Wold, O., Harun, F., Kostiukhin, A., Järveoja, M., Veske, M., Tamm, T., Voormansik, K., Olesk, A., Boccia, V., Longepe, N., & Cadau, E. G. (2021). *KappaMask*:

- AI-based cloudmask processor for Sentinel-2. *Remote Sensing*, 13(20), 4100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13204100>
- Dong, Z., Wang, G., Amankwah, S. O. Y., Wei, X., Hu, Y., & Feng, A. (2021). Monitoring the summer flooding in the Poyang Lake area of China in 2020 based on Sentinel-1 data and multiple convolutional neural networks. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 102, 102400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2021.102400>
- Du, Y., Zhang, Y., Ling, F., Wang, Q., Li, W., & Li, X. (2016). Water bodies' mapping from Sentinel-2 imagery with modified normalized difference water index at 10-m spatial resolution produced by sharpening the SWIR band. *Remote Sensing*, 8(4), 354. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8040354>
- EUR-Lex - Document 32017D0863 - EN. (2017). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/decimpl/2017/863/oj>
- European Commission, Centre, Joint Research. (2023). *GHSL data package 2023 (Nos. KJ-03-23-103-EN-N (online), KJ-03-23-103-EN-C (print))*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/098587>
- European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2003). *Public participation in relation to the water framework directive No 8*. OPOCE. <http://bookshop.europa.eu/uri?target=EUB:NOTICE:KH5103221:EN:HTML>
- European Commission, Eurostat. (2021). *Applying the degree of urbanisation - a methodological manual to define cities, towns and rural areas for international comparisons - 2021 edition*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2785/706535>
- European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2020). *Manual for CEMS-rapid mapping products: Valid for the portfolio since April 2019, status 31 August 2020*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/29876>
- European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2021). *Atlas of the human planet 2020: Open geoinformation for research, policy, and action*. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/16432>
- European Space Agency. (2024a). *SentiWiki Home - Sentiwiki.Copernicus.eu*. <https://sentiwiki.copernicus.eu/web/>
- European Space Agency. (2024b). *SNAP - ESA's SentiNel application platform - Github.com*. <https://github.com/senbox-org>
- Fletcher, T. D., Andrieu, H., & Hamel, P. (2013). Understanding, management and modelling of urban hydrology and its consequences for receiving waters: A state of the art. *Advances in Water Resources*, 51, 261–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2012.09.001>
- FloodList. (2021). *Over 350, 000 evacuated, 33 dead, 8 missing after Zhengzhou and Henan floods*. <https://floodlist.com/asia/china-henan-zhengzhou-floods-update-july-2021>
- Gao, F., Kustas, W. P., & Anderson, M. C. (2012). A data mining approach for sharpening thermal satellite imagery over land. *Remote Sensing*, 4(11), 3287–3319. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs4113287>
- Guzinski, R. (2024). *GitHub - Radosuav/PyDMS: Python implementation of data mining sharpener - Github.com*. <https://github.com/radosuav/pyDMS>
- IPCC. (2012). *Managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation. Special report of working groups I and II of the intergovernmental panel on climate change*. Cambridge University Press.
- Konapala, G., Kumar, S. V., & Khaliq Ahmad, S. (2021). Exploring Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 diversity for flood inundation mapping using deep learning. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry & Remote Sensing*, 180, 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2021.08.016>
- Lee, S. U., Chung, S. Y., & Park, R.-H. (1990). A comparative performance study of several global thresholding techniques for segmentation. *Computer Vision, Graphics and Image Processing*, 52(2), 171–190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0734-189X\(90\)90053-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0734-189X(90)90053-X)
- Li, J., Cai, Y., Li, Q., Kou, M., & Zhang, T. (2024). A review of remote sensing image segmentation by deep learning methods. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2024.2328827>
- Lin, T.-Y., Goyal, P., Girshick, R., He, K., & Dollár, P. (2018). *Focal loss for dense object detection*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1708.02002>
- Lin, Y., Bhardwaj, S.-H., Hill, A., & Hill, E. M. (2019). Urban flood detection with Sentinel-1 multi-temporal Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) observations in a Bayesian framework: A case study for hurricane Matthew. *Remote Sensing*, 11(15), 1778. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151778>

- Lindersson, S., Brandimarte, L., Mård, J., & DiBaldassarre, G. (2020). A review of freely accessible global datasets for the study of floods, droughts and their interactions with human societies. *WIREs Water*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1424>
- Ltd, KappaZeta. (2023). *GitHub - Kappazeta/Km predict: S2 full image prediction - Github.com*. <https://github.com/kappazeta/kmpredict>
- Mason, D. C., Dance, S. L., & Cloke, H. L. (2021). Floodwater detection in urban areas using Sentinel-1 and WorldDEM data. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JRS.15.032003>
- Mateo-García, G., Veitch-Michaelis, J., Smith, L., Oprea, S. V., Schumann, G., Gal, Y., Baydin, A. G., & Backes, D. (2021). Towards global flood mapping onboard low cost satellites with machine learning. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-86650-z>
- Montello, F., Arnaudo, E., & Rossi, C. (2022). Mmflood: A multimodal dataset for flood delineation from satellite imagery. *Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Access*, 10, 96774–96787. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3205419>
- Muszynski, M., Hölzer, T., Weiss, J., Fraccaro, P., Zortea, M., & Brunschweiler, T. (2022). Flood event detection from Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 data: Does land use matter for performance of U-Net based flood segmenters? *2022 IEEE International Conference on Big Data* (Vol. 17. pp. 4860–4867). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/bigdata55660.2022.10020911>
- Nemni, E., Bullock, J., Belabbes, S., & Bromley, L. (2020). Fully convolutional neural network for rapid flood segmentation in synthetic aperture radar imagery. *Remote Sensing*, 12(16), 2532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12162532>
- Notarangelo, N. M., Hirano, K., Albano, R., & Sole, A. (2021). Transfer learning with convolutional neural networks for rainfall detection in single images. *Water*, 13(5), 588. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13050588>
- Notarangelo, N. M., Mazzariello, A., Albano, R., & Sole, A. (2021). Comparing three machine learning techniques for building extraction from a digital surface model. *Applied Sciences*, 11(13), 6072. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11136072>
- Otsu, N. (1979). A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, 9(1), 62–66. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1979.4310076>
- Pesaresi, M., Ehrlich, D., Kemper, T., Siragusa, A., Florczyk, A. J., Freire, S., & Joint Research Centre European Commission. (2017) Atlas of the human planet 2017: Global exposure to natural hazards. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/709471>
- Portalés-Julià, E., Bountos, N. I., Sdraka, M., Mateo-García, G., Papoutsis, I., & GómezChova, L. (2024). Multimodal and multitemporal data fusion for flood extent segmentation exploiting Kurosiwo and WorldFloods Sentinel datasets. *IGARSS, 2024 - 2024 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing symposium* (pp. 950–953). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS53475.2024.10690461>
- Portalés-Julià, E., Mateo-García, G., Purcell, C., & Gómez-Chova, L. (2023). Global flood extent segmentation in optical satellite images. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-47595-7>
- Powers, D. M. W. (2020). *Evaluation: From precision, recall and f-measure to roc, informedness, markedness and correlation*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2010.16061>
- Rahneemofar, M., Chowdhury, T., Sarkar, A., Varshney, D., Yari, M., & Murphy, R. R. (2020). Floodnet: A high resolution aerial imagery dataset for post flood scene understanding. *Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Access*, 9, 89644–89654. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3090981>
- Rambour, C., Audebert, N., Koeniguer, E., Le Saux, B., Crucianu, M., & Datcu, M. (2020). SEN12-FLOOD : A SAR and Multispectral dataset for flood detection. IEEE Dataport. <https://doi.org/10.21227/w6xz-s898>
- Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P., & Brox, T. (2015). *U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1505.04597>
- Rudner, T. G. J., Rußwurm, M., Fil, J., Pelich, R., Bischke, B., Kopačková, V., & Biliński, P. (2019). Multi3Net: Segmenting Flooded buildings via fusion of multiresolution, multisensor, and multi-temporal satellite imagery. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* (Vol. 33. pp. 702–709). <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v33i01.3301702>

- Saleh, A., Yuzir, A., & Abustan, I. (2020). Flood mapping using Sentinel-1 SAR Imagery: Case study of the November 2017 flood in Penang. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 479, pp. 012013). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/479/1/012013>
- Tarpanelli, A., Mondini, A. C., & Camici, S. (2022). Effectiveness of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 for flood detection assessment in Europe. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22(8), 2473–2489. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2473-2022>
- Tavus, B., Can, R., & Kocaman, S. (2022). A CNN-based flood mapping approach using Sentinel-1 data. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*, 549–556. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-annals-V-3-2022-549-2022>
- United Nations. (2021). *Deadly flooding, heatwaves in Europe, highlight urgency of climate action*. <https://news.un.org/en/story/2021/07/1096012>
- Vanama, V. S. K., Mandal, D., & Rao, Y. S. (2020). GEE4FLOOD: Rapid mapping of flood areas using temporal Sentinel-1 SAR images with Google Earth Engine cloud platform. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 14(3), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JRS.14.034505>
- Van Rossum, G., & Drake, F. L., Jr. (1995). *Python reference manual*. Centrum voor Wiskunde en Informatica Amsterdam.
- Wang, P., Zhang, G., & Leung, H. (2019). Improving super-resolution flood inundation mapping for multispectral remote sensing image by supplying more spectral information. *IEEE Geoscience & Remote Sensing Letters*, 16(5), 771–775. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2018.2882516>
- Wieland, M., & Martinis, S. (2019). A modular processing chain for automated flood monitoring from multi-spectral satellite data. *Remote Sensing*, 11(19), 2330. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11192330>
- Wilby, R. L. (2019). A global hydrology research agenda fit for the 2030s. *Hydrology Research*, 50(6), 1464–1480. <https://doi.org/10.2166/nh.2019.100>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Mons, B., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., & Zhao, J. (2016). The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wirion, C., Bauwens, W., & Verbeiren, B. (2017). Location-and time-specific hydrological simulations with multi-resolution remote sensing data in urban areas. *Remote Sensing*, 9(7), 645. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9070645>
- World Economic Forum. (2022). *The global risks report 2022*. <https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-risks-report-2022/>
- Yimer, E. A., Yadollahi, S., Riakhi, F.-E., Alitane, A., Weerasinghe, I., Wirion, C., Nossent, J., & van Griensven, A. (2023). A groundwater level-based filtering to improve the accuracy of locating agricultural tile drain and ditch networks. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 122, 103423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2023.103423>
- Yokoya, N., Yamanoi, K., He, W., Baier, G., Adriano, B., Miura, H., & Oishi, S. (2020). *Breaking the limits of remote sensing by simulation and deep learning for flood and debris flow mapping*. arXiv: 2006.05180 [cs, eess]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.05180>
- Youden, W. J. (1950). Index for rating diagnostic tests. *Cancer: Interdisciplinary International Journal of the American Cancer Society*, 3(1), 32–35. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142\(1950\)3:1<32::AID-CNCR2820030106>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-0142(1950)3:1<32::AID-CNCR2820030106>3.0.CO;2-3)
- Yu, H., Yang, Z., Tan, L., Wang, Y., Sun, W., Sun, M., & Tang, Y. (2018). Methods and datasets on semantic segmentation: A review. *Neurocomputing*, 304, 82–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2018.03.037>
- Yuan, X., Shi, J., & Gu, L. (2021). A review of deep learning methods for semantic segmentation of remote sensing imagery. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 169, 114417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.114417>

- Zanaga, D., Van De Kerchove, R., Daems, D., De Keersmaecker, W., Brockmann, C., Kirches, G., & Arino, O. (2022). ESA WorldCover 10 m 2021 v200 [Data set] Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254221>
- Zhao, J., Li, Y., Matgen, P., Pelich, R., Hostache, R., & Wagner, W. (2022). Urban-aware U-Net for large-scale urban flood mapping using multitemporal Sentinel-1 intensity and interferometric coherence. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience & Remote Sensing*, 60, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2022.3230378>
- Zhao, J., Xiong, Z., & Zhu, X. X. (2024). UrbanSARFloods: Sentinel-1 SLC-Based benchmark dataset for urban and open-area flood mapping arXiv e-print. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.04111>